

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF A HYBRID SYSTEM FOR ENHANCEMENT OF FLEXURAL STRENGTH OF REINFORCED CONCRETE BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

Strengthening limits in FRP design codes aim at preventing catastrophic failures of the structure if the FRP is damaged. Keeping to this philosophy, this study focuses on a hybrid scheme, that comprises section enlargement of a RC beam with new reinforcement, stronger concrete and FRP for flexural enhancement. Four RC beams were tested, one as a control, and three with progressive schemes combining enlargement and FRP. The failure modes, the interfacial behavior and FRP failure were studied. The findings were used to assess the suitability of existing analytical methods for hybrid structures, and for the development of simplified analytical methods.

KEYWORDS

FRP; Hybrid strengthening; Debonding; Retrofitting

INTRODUCTION

The design philosophies for FRP converge on establishing a ‘safe limit’ for the extent of enhancement. When incorporated with such limits, a significant reduction in the full potential of FRP is observed. Design guides such as [1] state “increase in overall flexural strength from 10 to 160 percent have been documented”, however, “When taking into account the strengthening limits of 9.2 and ductility and serviceability limits, however, strength increases of up to 40 percent are more reasonable”.

The objectives of establishing strength limits are based on the fundamental concept of that loss of contribution of FRP to a structural element during the service state should not lead to a catastrophic failure. In practice, if FRP is unable to achieve the required level of strengthening due to these limits, conventional strengthening methods, such as section enlargement or steel plate bonding, are adopted. However, such conventional strengthening methods are far more difficult to implement and inefficient mainly due to the enlargement sizes and the number of steps involved.

This study is aimed at developing a design blueprint to be used in practice for a hybrid strengthening scheme for flexural strengthening, i.e. a combination of enlargement and FRP, which is far more lean and efficient compared to pure section enlargement. It explores the suitability of using current analytical models and develops a simplified analytical model to design a hybrid strengthening scheme for flexural enhancement of an R.C beam.

FRP DESIGN APPROACH

Both [1] and [2] take a limit state approach when it comes to the philosophy of the design. A set of calculations is then proposed to address all possible failure modes and to ensure that the final stress and strain of FRP is well within its recommended values.

In general, an iterative process involving balancing of tension and compressive forces of the section with the FRP is used where the beam section is assumed to have a linear strain profile and the following key aspects are evaluated.

Concrete crushing, yielding of tensile rebar and FRP strains

The maximum compressive strength of the concrete should not exceed its maximum failure strain (e.g. 0.003 or 0.0035). The fundamentals of RC beam design require an ‘under-reinforced’ section where the steel yields prior to concrete crushing. However, when FRP is placed in the tension zone, the calculation needs to be adjusted, should tensile stress or the shear stresses exceed the limits. At this point, the concrete will not reach its ultimate failure strain and therefore, the factors used for the equivalent concrete stress block to calculate the compressive force in concrete should not be used.

Different guides approach this in varying methods, [1] calls for a modified rectangular stress block, whereas [2] calls for use of appropriate stress-strain diagrams with a parabolic relationship.

Ductility

The ductility of the FRP strengthened section is achieved not only by yielding of steel but also by ensuring a minimum strain limit has been met. In [1], a lower strength reduction factor is recommended for sections where steel strain does not exceed 0.005.

However, when it comes to traditional strengthening methods such as enlarging section, where the depth of the beam is increased, ductility criteria can easily be achieved as the effective depth of the beam section increases.

FRP Rupture

While this is a rare phenomenon for EB schemes, due to the nature of RC beams, FRP can be ruptured if the maximum strain of the FRP is exceeded due to bending stresses and localized stress increases due to flexural cracks.

FRP Debonding

Debonding of FRP is one of the well-known failure modes which can be categorized into 2 broad categories; separation of FRP from the substrate and cover-delamination.

Separation of FRP from the substrate

The separation of the FRP could occur due to the presence of shear cracks and due to the longitudinal shear stresses in both the steel yield region and the elastic region of the beams. In this case, the separation would progress through cement matrix or the adhesive layer, showcasing a clear and clean separation of FRP from the substrate.

Cover Delamination

The phenomenon where concrete cover starting to separate while still attached to FRP, at the termination points, is known as cover delamination. Sufficient anchorage length or ‘U-Wrap’ anchorage needs to be provided to prevent this type of failure.

HYBRID STRENGTHENING SCHEME

A hybrid strengthening scheme proposed in this study consists of both section enlargement and FRP. If the sectional enlargement alone is used, the final geometries of the section could be undesired for aesthetic and/or in some cases to meet the regulatory requirements. In addition, an enlargement proposal to enhance flexural strength may not be helpful in increasing the section’s shear capacity. As such, combining FRP with an enlarged section provides a lean but effective design where each strengthening scheme would be complimentary to each other.

Figure 1 is an example of a proposed enlargement scheme to enhance the flexural capacity. The following aspects require due consideration during the design process;

Figure 1: Example of an Enlargement Scheme

Combining Materials with Different Strengths

The existing section of the beam consists of old concrete and reinforcement compared to the enlarged portion where the beam would have newer and stronger concrete with new tensile reinforcement likely to exceed the strength of the existing rebars.

Interfacial Shear Stresses

Introduction of a new 'layer' of concrete results in additional interfacial shear stress between the new and old concrete.

Figure 2 illustrates a hybrid scheme where FRP is incorporated to the enlarged beam.

Figure 2: Example of an Enlargement Scheme with FRP

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup consisted of a total of 4 specimens, where it was carefully designed to observe the failure modes in a progressive manner. Four beams with dimensions of 300mm (width) x 500mm (depth) were casted first with a lower concrete grade of 16/20MPa. Diameter 20mm reinforcement bars, where three on the compression side and another three on the tension side were provided as longitudinal reinforcement. 2-legged stirrups with 10mm diameter rebars were spaced at 200mm centre to centre were used as the links. The specified ultimate strength of all the reinforcement bars used was 500MPa. The first beam, which was the Control Specimen, was tested with no changes to its dimensions and reinforcement details (Figure 4, Section A-A).

The second specimen was an Enlarged Section, where the depth of the beam was increased by 100mm by adding a new layer of concrete with reinforcement. When installing the new longitudinal reinforcement, three reinforcement bars of diameter 13mm, a new link was installed using a chemical anchor to facilitate the shear transfer between old and new concrete. Total two 10mm diameter reinforcement bars which, were bent as L-bars bars, spaced at 200mm were installed as links by drilling holes on to the tensile face of the beam and using a chemical anchor. The new flexural reinforcement was then attached to these links. The new layer of concrete was substantially stronger than what was previously used, with a strength of 40/50MPa, to simulate the typical case of beam enlargement (Figure 4, Section B-B).

The third and fourth specimens were casted similarly to the second beam but with the addition of FRP, making them hybrid beams. For the third specimen, Hybrid-3, layers of flexural FRP were added on the exposed face of the new concrete layer, which is the extreme tensile face (Figure 4, Section C-C). The fourth specimen, Hybrid-4, consisted of the same amount of flexural FRP but with an addition of ‘U-Wraps’ at the ends for additional anchorage (Figure 4, Section D-D). Table 1 summarises the tested properties of the concrete and reinforcement bars (tested accordance to SS560 – 2016).

Table 1: Material Properties

Material	Cylinder Strength (MPa)	Yield Strength (MPa)
C16/20	19.9	-
C40/50	41.66	-
Steel (20mm)	-	561
Steel (13mm)	-	582
Steel (10mm)	-	610

The FRP used in this case is a Tyfo SEH51a, a Glass FRP System, with a modulus of 26100MPa, ultimate elongation of 2.2% and with an ultimate tensile strength of 575MPa. The total composite thickness of the flexural FRP was 2.6mm for both Hybrid-3 and Hybrid-4 specimens, and the composite thickness of the U-Wrap anchorage in specimen Hybrid-4 was 1.3mm.

In all cases, the beams were 5.5m in length with a span of 5m with a 4-point loading set-up. A 4-point loading set-up allowed for a uniform shear force at the ends of the beams. The spacing between the loading points was 1.668m. Please refer to Figure 3 for the experimental set-up.

Figure 3: Experimental set-up

Figure 4: Key Cross-Sections of Beams

THEORITCAL ANALYSIS

Table 3 summarizes the theoretical flexural capacities of the specimens. These capacities were calculated using absolute material properties, without the consideration of any safety factors. A load balancing approach, where the tensile forces of the section were equal to the compressive forces was adopted.

Table 2: Theoretical Capacities

Specimen	Theoretical Moment Capacity	EC2 Simplified Moment Capacity
Control	218.9 kNm	218.8 kNm
Enlarged	332.7 kNm	323.1 kNm
Hybrid-3	412.9 kNm	-

Tensile strength of the concrete was disregarded for specimens while the ultimate failure strain of the concrete was taken as 0.0035. The stress-strain relationship provided in Figure 3.3 of [3] was used to obtain the stress of the concrete, while strength of the steel was limited to its yield strength. In all cases, the strains of all materials, concrete, steel and FRP were considered as directly proportional to their distances from the neutral axis, i.e. plane sections remain plane after loading. The failure point for both Control and Enlarged sections was taken as when the concrete reaches its failure strain. The rebars were yielded at this point, which confirmed that the ductility of the section has been met.

The capacities established from using the simplified design method described in [3] are provided for comparison. The simplified method adopts an equivalent rectangular stress block where the height of it is limited to 0.8 of neutral axis for concrete grades lower than 50MPa (cylinder). No material safety factors were adopted when establishing these values for direct comparison.

A similar type of theoretical framework was applied to the Enlarged section, assuming that there will be no interfacial shear failures at the joint between old and new concrete. The final strain of extreme tensile steel was 0.0193.

Interfacial shear stress between old and new concrete was intended to be resisted by the new links post-installed with chemical anchors. The configuration of the post-installed links proposed in this experimental set-up does not contribute to the shear strength of the section effectively, as such it was not considered as part of the links providing the shear strength to the section.

The manufacturers of the chemical anchor, Hilti provides the guidance on the effective tensile and shear strengths to be used in the design. Typically, the strength of the concrete, drill depth, edge distance and spacing between links are the fundamental factors affecting the strength of the design. The simplified methods proposed in [4] provide an ultimate design shear strength of for a diameter of 10mm reinforcement bars installed with using the Hilti RE-500 V3 chemical anchor.

As the shear force on the ends of this 4-point loading set-up is constant at the ends, the interfacial shear stress between the interface of old and new concrete will remain constant. As such, the total number of links required to transfer the shearing stresses can be established assuming a uniform distribution. The experimental results were later used to validate this assumption.

For those specimens with the flexural FRP, the theoretical calculations assumed a failure strain of 0.008 for flexural FRP in all cases, which is provided as a general recommendation in [2] though the design strain for the FRP system described in Table 2 was 0.0094 as per the guidelines of the same code. While it was expected FRP to reach higher strains before failure, limit for the strains were established to account for unpredictability of the exact nature of FRP failure at higher strains where steel is expected to be yielded and section with cracks. As such, FRP was expected to reach its failure strain before other materials. The calculations indicated that at the failure strain of FRP, the extreme compressive fibre of concrete has not reached its ultimate strain of 0.0035, but only 0.002342. Extreme tensile steel was found to be yielded with a strain of 0.007101.

The section Hybrid-4, which incorporates the FRP U-Wrap for additional anchorage, was assumed to have the same theoretical capacity as Hybrid-3 in order to verify the effectiveness of the anchorage through experimental data.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental load-deflection relationships for all 4 specimens are shown in Figure 5. All specimens exhibited a similar stiffness value till the cracking moment. However, upon reaching the cracking point, enlarged and hybrid specimens showed an increase in stiffness till the yield point.

Figure 5: Load-Deflection Curves

Table 4 summarises the actual capacities of beam elements.

Table 3: Experimental Results

Specimen	Tested Moment Capacity	Extreme concrete compression strain	Extreme tensile steel strain	Deflection at max. load (mm)
Control	220 kNm	0.00185	0.00398	83.85
Enlarged	359 kNm	0.002956	0.03093	117.56
Hybrid-3	410 kNm	0.001779	0.13651	49.28
Hybrid-4	457 kNm	0.001699	0.01218	76.06

The experimental values for both Control and Enlarged sections were within the margin of 10%, with theoretical values yielding lower results. The maximum compressive strain of concrete for the Control section was well below the ultimate failure strain of the concrete of 0.0035 while the steel has yielded with a measured strain of 0.00398 (Figure 6). Similar type of result was observed for the enlarged section, with steel showing a higher strain value yet the maximum compressive strain of concrete strain has not reached its ultimate strain (Figure 7). In both cases, the sections were ductile.

Figure 6: Failure of Control Specimen

Figure 7: Failure of Enlarged Section

Hybrid-3 section failed due to the debonding of FRP and the separation cracks between old and new concrete were more prominent (Figure 8). The adaptation of maximum strain of 0.008 was proven to be critical, as the experimental capacity of the section was almost on par with the theoretical value. The compressive strain of concrete was significantly lower than the theoretical value and the measured steel showed a significant increase in the strain. Overall, it showed a ductile failure of the section, with FRP contributing to an additional 14% increase of the capacity.

Figure 8: Failure of specimen Hybrid-3 with debonding of FRP

Inclusion of U-Wrap anchorage significantly delayed failure of the FRP in Hybrid-4 section (Figure 9). It enhanced the overall capacity by 27% compared to the Enlarged section or an additional 11% compared to the section without any anchorage. The U-Wrap FRP did not fail when the flexural FRP was debonding and it exhibited resistance of flexural-shear cracks at the beam ends.

Figure 9: Failure of the specimen Hybrid-4 with debonding of FRP

Figure 10: Behavior of U-Wrap anchorage FRP

Horizontal cracks at the interface between old and new concrete were observed together with the flexural cracks. However, Enlarged and both Hybrid sections did not show a complete separation failure of the old and new concrete. Further, there were no signs of overstressing of a single post-installed links showing any localised ‘pull-out’ effect of a post-installed link.

ANLYTICAL METHOD FOR A HYBRID SECTION

The design of Hybrid section should be focused on ductility, interfacial shear between old and new concrete and design of FRP. As the design of FRP involves an iterative process, the following framework provides a guidance.

Design strain of flexural FRP

The design strain of FRP is to be established based on the design code considered. However, the final design strain of FRP is not to exceed 0.008, regardless of the material. If the design strain of FRP is less than 0.008, the lower value to be used.

The design strain of the FRP to be fixed, with a linear strain distribution across the section is adopted.

Ductility

For a hybrid scheme, a check on ductility is recommended by limiting the neutral axis depth and ensuring steel has yielded. For a starting point for the calculation, a neutral axis depth is defined from the following equation to be used.

$$x \leq \frac{d}{1 + \frac{\varepsilon_y}{\varepsilon_c}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where x is the neutral axis, ε_c is the ultimate failure strain of concrete, ε_y is the yield strain of the extreme tensile steel and d is the effective depth of the new section. The neutral axis should not exceed the value established in Equation 1 and could be adjusted to a lower value should the specific design codes requires for it.

Interfacial Shear

The maximum interfacial shear stress is to be established using the expected design shear force and properties. The maximum shear capacity of a shear connector is established based on the installation method and manufacturer’s recommendations. The minimum number of shear connectors required for the section in consideration is established assuming a uniform distribution of interfacial shear stress.

Iteration

Upon establishing the FRP strain and neutral axis height, the forces in the section to be established using material stress-strain values. For concrete compression, use of a parabolic stress-strain relationship is recommended. The value of the extreme concrete compression strain is to be adjusted till the force balance is achieved. However, based on theoretical analysis and experimental results, an upper limit of $0.8\varepsilon_c$ for the strain of extreme compression fibre of the section is recommended.

Strength Reduction Factor

A global strength reduction factor (ϕ), as provided in [1] is recommended. Should the strain of extreme tensile steel exceed 0.005, a global strength reduction factor of 0.9 is to be applied. For strains between 0.005 and yield strain, a linearly varying factor between 0.9 and 0.65 as shown in Equation 10.2.7 of [1] is to be applied. For all other cases, a factor of 0.65 is recommended.

Figure 11: Analytical Model for Hybrid Schemes

The above-mentioned analytical approach result in a calculated capacity of 373.5kN for section Hybrid-3 with a maximum strain of 0.008 for FRP. The experimental results proved that the section Hybrid-3 possess a higher capacity. This analytical approach calculates a conservative value prior to the incorporation of material safety factors and other safety factors recommended in the relevant codes of practice.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on established theoretical methods and novel experimental results involving Enlarged and Hybrid strengthening schemes, following are established.

The simplified analytical methods for section analysis described in [3] could be applied to an enlarged section provided that the limits on the neutral axis have been met and tensile steel has yielded. Otherwise, the geometry and reinforcement details of the enlarged section need to be adjusted till the conditions are met.

Limiting the strain of FRP at the ultimate state to 0.008 or lower, depending on the design strain of the FRP material as recommended by codes adopted, has been further validated for a hybrid section. This establishes the starting point for the iterative calculation procedure.

Incorporation of FRP U-Wraps almost instantly increased the capacity of the section by further 11%. An additional enhancement factor of 1.1 is recommended for a hybrid scheme which has a sole focus on flexural strengthening and provided with U-Wrap anchorage from the same material at both ends for at least 30% of the total length measured at each end.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.